

Understanding the Police Responses to Victims of Human Trafficking in the United Kingdom.

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DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.15863062 | ISSN: 2977-1676

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www.journalcjd.org

British Library Registered ISSN: 2977-1676

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15863062>

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The Journal of
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Acknowledgements

This dissertation would not have been possible without the help and support of many people, to whom I am deeply grateful.

First and foremost, I would like to express my sincere gratitude to my supervisor, Shovita Dhakal Adhikari, for her guidance and feedback throughout my dissertation. Her extensive knowledge and experience have been invaluable in shaping the direction and completion of this dissertation.

I would also like to extend my heartfelt thanks to my professor, Angie Phoenix, who has been a source of inspiration and motivation throughout my academic years. Her belief in my potential and her encouragement to pursue this particular topic played a pivotal role in developing my dissertation. Her constructive criticism and valuable comments helped me refine my ideas and strengthen my arguments, shaping them in a much better way than I had originally planned. Beyond her role as a professor, she has been a mentor and a trusted confidante.

To my dear friends Ioana and Joselyn, words cannot fully express how grateful I am to have you both in my life. Thank you for all of your encouragement and support of this journey.

A special thank you goes to my family. To my beloved mother Angelina, thank you for your unconditional love and understanding. Your patience and support throughout my academic journey have been a great source of strength. To my brother Antonio, thank you for always being there for me and supporting me in every way you could. Finally, my deepest appreciation goes to my partner, Ardit, whose love, patience, and constant encouragement have helped carry me through this entire process. Your belief in me and your presence through every stage of this journey have been my greatest source of strength. Without your continued support, this dissertation would not have been possible.

Abstract

This research aims to understand how the police in the United Kingdom respond to victims of human trafficking, how well they identify and support victims, and what challenges police face. These aims are important given the complex nature of human trafficking, which is driven by global push and pull factors such as poverty and demand for cheap labour and sexual services. While the Modern Slavery Act 2015 and the National Referral Mechanism have strengthened the institutional response, significant issues remain. Both the police and existing legal frameworks often misidentify (e.g., as migrant smugglers and prostitutes) and criminalise victims, have deficient police training, and lack effective multi-agency cooperation. Some progress has occurred, but structural obstacles remain to prevent victim-oriented and trauma-sensitive approaches. The study presents recommendations that aim to improve victim protection methods and enhance police operations. The study adopts a library-based methodology, relying on secondary sources such as academic journals, government publications, and NGO reports to provide a comprehensive overview of the current landscape and ongoing debates.

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Chapter 1: Introduction

1.1 Introduction

Human trafficking (HT) is one of the most serious crimes worldwide, second only to drug and weapons trafficking (Keatinge and Barry, 2017). It is one of the fastest-growing criminal businesses due to its low risk and high-profit potential (ibid.). HT disproportionately affects women and children, although men and boys are also trafficked. People become victims of exploitation through coercive methods that combine deception with power abuse. These methods are used to compel individuals into forced labour or sexual exploitation or crime-related activities, or modern-day servitude roles (UN, 2000; Home Office, 2024).

Internationally, the adoption of the Palermo Protocol (2000), along with the UK national definition, has marked a milestone in the fight against human trafficking. It established a common definition and outlined states' obligations for prevention, protection, and prosecution (UNHCR, 2006). Over the last few years, the UK authorities have strengthened their response by developing new measures to protect their victims.

Key among these are the Modern Slavery Act (MSA) 2015 and the National Referral Mechanism (NRM), which serve as fundamental mechanisms that help identify trafficking victims, followed by their protection and support provision (Home Office, 2020). Despite the new anti-trafficking structures, multiple barriers exist for implementing these responses, particularly for police departments (Findlay, 2024). Research demonstrates that police officers stand as first responders for trafficking victims, yet evidence shows repeatedly problematic methods used by police departments to identify and assist victims. Lack of clear definitions of trafficking combined with insufficient training and cultural prejudices, have resulted in inconsistent policing responses that often misclassify, criminalise, or entirely overlook victims, causing further harm (Skolnick, 1966; Bittner, 1967; Laczko and Gramengna, 2003; Clawson et al., 2004; Pajon and Walsh, 2022). Furthermore, the structural parameters that block information exchange between agencies and the implementation of trauma-sensitive defence procedures result in more hurdles for victims when they try to get assistance.

Police entities tend to label trafficking victims in sex work and county lines drug gangs together with illegal immigrants as criminal offenders, over victims whose protection needs must be recognised (Davies, 2009; Doezema, 2010; Farrell and Pfeffer, 2014; Mason and agencies, 2016; Davis, 2019;

Hestia, 2019). This approach undermines the UK's commitment to protecting vulnerable individuals and securing justice against traffickers. Furthermore, the most attention has been given to the sexual exploitation of women and girls; other forms, such as labour trafficking and the exploitation of men and boys, have often been overlooked (Gulati, 2012; Home Office, 2024). This selective focus has led to an incomplete understanding of the issue and has left many victims inadequately supported by the current framework.

1.2 Research Aims

This study aims to understand and critically assess the police responses to victims of human trafficking in the United Kingdom. In particular, it seeks to examine the challenges law enforcement faces in identifying and supporting victims. It also aims to explore the impact of existing legislation and the effectiveness of multi-agency collaboration efforts.

1.3 Research Objectives

The research objectives of this research where:

1. What challenges do UK police face in identifying and supporting victims of human trafficking? How do the legislations and police respond to these vulnerable victims? Why do victims not cooperate with police?
2. How effective are the UK's current human trafficking interventions in practice? What strategies are used to implement these interventions, and what challenges affect their success?

1.4 Methodology and Ethics Considerations

This study adopts a library-based approach, relying on secondary research by analysing existing academic literature. It combined academic journal articles, books, eBooks, government reports, NGO publications, and legal documents to gather information on the topic. Secondary research is more accessible since the data has already been collected and analysed by other researchers (Davies and Francis, 2018). Also, it provides access to high-quality data during limited timeframes and resource limitations (Clark et al., 2021; Crowther-Dowey and Fussey, 2013). Finally, secondary research is a more appropriate approach to carrying out the project because human trafficking is a sensitive topic, and interviewing victims or police officers can be ethically complex and practically challenging.

Nevertheless, this approach also presents limitations, such as potential data quality issues and limited control over the original collection process (Clark et al., 2021).

This library-based research project did not need formal ethical approval because it did not involve direct interaction with vulnerable individuals. The secondary sources used were produced by researchers who had already followed the ethical guidelines set out in the British Society of Criminology Statement of Ethics (2015).

1.5 Structure of the Dissertation

The dissertation is structured into an introduction, three chapters, a conclusion, and recommendations, each addressing key aspects of the research's aims and objectives.

Chapter 2 critically reviews the existing literature to explore frameworks for understanding responses to the phenomenon of human trafficking. It reviews international and domestic definitions of human trafficking to understand ongoing debates around victimhood, exploitation, and the complexities involved in identifying trafficking cases. Difficulties in measuring the true scale of trafficking, gendered patterns of exploitation, causes of trafficking, and the physical and psychological harms endured by victims are presented.

Chapter 3 analyses the existing anti-trafficking regulations in policy documents and legal frameworks of the UK. The Modern Slavery Act 2015 and the National Referral Mechanism undergo analysis to assess their positive aspects, together with ongoing challenges. Child criminal exploitation, particularly county lines, despite the expanded scope in the NRM, still, the exact number remains unknown. Particular attention is paid to gaps in victim support, delays in decision-making processes, and the tensions between immigration enforcement and victim protection. The analysis exposes fundamental problems that exist between the written laws and the actual application of policies and procedures by law enforcement officers nationwide.

Chapter 4 critically assesses the police response to victims of human trafficking. It explores the difficulties police encounter when recognising victims alongside the problems victims have with self-identification as well as the sustained issue of mistaken classification, which leads to criminalisation. This part of the text examines flaws in police training programs while showing gaps in law enforcement awareness and their limited cooperation with different organisations, further involving inadequate trauma-sensitive policing standards.

Chapter 5 will provide the outcome of key findings and will offer recommendations for future research.

Chapter 2: Understanding Human Trafficking

2.1 Introduction

This chapter provides an understanding of human trafficking and will discuss the key debates around exploitation. It covers the Palermo Protocol (2000) and UK definitions, its criticisms, and challenges in measuring trafficking's true scale. Efforts have been made to discuss the key theoretical perspective, 'push and pull', that drives people into trafficking. Lastly, it addresses the severe physical and psychological harm faced by victims, including PTSD and long-term trauma.

2.2 What is Human Trafficking?

Human trafficking functions as a severe modern slavery practice which violates fundamental human rights by exploiting vulnerable individuals, often for the purpose of financial gain (Kelly and Regan, 2000). Traffickers exploit adults and children for the purpose and intent of sex exploitation and forced labour or organ harvesting through force, fraud, or coercion (HMICFRS, 2017; Home Office, 2025b). Trafficking in persons occurs both internationally and within the UK, meaning crossing borders is not necessary for trafficking to take place (Kumar, 2015; Burke et al., 2022).

Internationally, the United Nations adopted the Protocol to Prevent, Suppress and Punish Trafficking in Persons, Especially Women and Children, shortened to the Palermo Protocol (UN, 2000). This definition is applied by over 180 countries, including the UK (Laczko and Goździak, 2005; U.S. Department of State, 2023). In Article 3 of this protocol, human trafficking is defined as:

“Trafficking in persons” shall mean the recruitment, transportation, transfer, harbouring or receipt of persons, by means of the threat or force or other forms of coercion, of abduction, of fraud, of deception, of the abuse of power, or of a position of vulnerability or of the giving or receiving of payments or benefits to achieve the consent of a person having control over another person, for the purpose of exploitation. Exploitation shall include, at a minimum, the exploitation of the prostitution of others or other forms of sexual exploitation, forced labour or services, slavery or practices similar to slavery, servitude, or the removal of organs” (UNODC, 2000; UNODC, 2013, p.1).

Nevertheless, despite its wide-ranging inclusion of the different forms of exploitation, the Palermo Protocol's (2000) definition has been criticised for being too broad and vague (Hyland, 2001; Seideman, 2015; Bales et al., 2020). This has caused confusion and inconsistency across countries, as the Protocol's ambiguity has led practitioners and scholars to create their own definitions (Richard, 1999; Hyland, 2001; Laczko and Gramegna, 2003; Clawson and Dutch, 2008; Seideman, 2015; Blitz and Simic, 2019; Farrell and De Vries, 2020; Jones, 2020). This has resulted in ineffective prevention strategies and inconsistent identification of trafficking cases. Similarly, the definition maintains limited effectiveness because it ignores trafficking complexities and focuses solely on force and fraud, alongside coercion (Warren, 2007; Aronowitz, 2017; Gallagher, 2001, 2017). This narrow perspective complicates efforts to address the issue effectively, as it tends to overlook the subtler forms of exploitation that frequently arise in trafficking situations (Warren, 2007). For instance, many victims are not only physically restrained or overly threatened, but are instead psychologically manipulated or coerced into exploitation (Kara, 2010). These victims may not fit the traditional definition of trafficking, making it difficult for police officers to identify and prosecute their traffickers (Papadouka, 2023). Equally, the UN definition fails to recognise the role that demand plays in perpetuating trafficking. The definition overweighs the supply side of trafficking by criminalising the actions of traffickers. While this approach is essential, it fails to address the demand for trafficked persons (ibid.). Traffickers engage in trafficking because there is a market for the exploitation of human beings. Until demand for exploitative labour and sex diminishes, trafficking will continue to thrive (Farrell, 2009). Additionally, the Protocol has been criticised for neglecting male victims, as it does not mention men and prioritises mainly women and children (Shoaps, 2013). This reinforces the misconception that men are unlikely victims, despite evidence from the NRM indicating that labour trafficking, which predominantly affects men, is widespread (World Health Organization, 2012; NCA, 2019a; ONS, 2020a). This exclusion of male victims, combined with weak enforcement, undermines the protocol's overall effectiveness.

Domestically, in England and Wales, HT is defined under the Modern Slavery Act 2015 as:

“A person commits the offence if the person arranges or facilitates the travel of another person (“V”) with a view to V being exploited” (legislation.gov.uk, 2015, no pg.).

The legal definitions above are made up of three essential components: The action refers to what is being done (e.g. recruitment, transportation, transfer, harbouring, or receipt of persons), means how the harm is done (e.g. threat or use of force, coercion, abduction, fraud, deception, abuse of power, or

vulnerability), and purpose why it is done (e.g. sexual exploitation, forced labour or domestic servitude, slavery, financial exploitation, and removal of organs) (Lee, 2011; Cockbain, 2018; Home Office, 2025b).

While the Modern Slavery Act 2015 includes “slavery” as part of the purpose of exploitation, Bales et al. (2011) argue that HT is not a form of slavery, but a process of enslavement. In contrast, Lee (2011) views HT as a contemporary form of slavery, since victims often end up in conditions of extreme control and forced labour. However, Kempadoo (2005) critiques this emphasis on slavery, arguing that while it highlights violence and exploitation, it risks sensationalism and confusion over terminology. Some prefer the term slavery-like practices to avoid confusion between legal enslavement and forced, waged labour.

The UK definition of HT also differs from the Palermo Protocol, as it does not include aspects like fraud, coercion, or benefit. However, there is a consensus that recruitment and exploitation are key. Clarifying the irrelevance of consent could help reduce confusion among UK police regarding victim consent (Home Office, 2024; Farrell et al., 2010). The absence of consent in the Protocol's definition has led to ongoing confusion between smuggling and trafficking (Farrell et al., 2010). For clarification, smuggling refers to the transportation of a consenting person for illegal entry into a country for profit, and their relationship ends upon arrival at the destination (Aronowitz, 2001; Farrell et al., 2010). In contrast, trafficking victims do not consent to their movement. Even when individuals initially agree to be smuggled, abuse, coercion, or deception can turn the situation into trafficking (Farrell et al., 2010). As a result, it is understandable that police officers may mistakenly categorise foreign trafficking victims as illegal migrants (*ibid.*). Another concern is the risk of unintended consequences, including increased human rights violations and vulnerability for migrants. By criminalising migrant smuggling, legislation may inadvertently push smugglers to adopt more risky methods, thereby endangering the lives of migrants (Bilger et al., 2006; Campana and Gelsthorpe, 2021). Gallagher (2001) emphasises that legal frameworks should prioritise addressing the underlying factors driving migration instead of penalising those who assist migrants in their journeys.

2.3 The Nature and Scope of Human Trafficking

Human trafficking affects nearly every country globally, either as a source, transit, or destination state, involving the key elements of recruitment, movement, and exploitation (Burke et al., 2022). However, due to its hidden nature, it has proven difficult to measure its true prevalence, with victim numbers increasing rapidly (Laczko and Gramengna, 2003). Despite this, estimates of the prevalence of HT have been made by the Walk Free Foundation. Their latest Global Slavery Index (2023a) in 2021 estimated

globally 49.6 million people trapped in modern slavery. Of these, 1 in 4 are children, 54% are women and girls; 27.6 million are exploited for forced labour (12% are children) (Stop the Traffik, nd); 22 million are in forced marriage (Global Slavery Index, 2023a); and 4.8 million persons in forced sexual exploitation (Stop the Traffik, nd).

In the UK, according to the latest Global Slavery Index (2023b), data released in July 2022, estimated that the number of potential victims of HT was 122,000. However, it is widely acknowledged that these figures are likely to be significant underestimations of the true scale of HT within the UK (HMICFRS, 2017; ONS, 2020a). This is because data collection is often limited to small-scale operations in specific geographical areas, focusing on particular types of trafficking without a consistent national approach (Scullion, 2015); lack of or limited anti-trafficking legislation; and the absence of or limited enforcement (Farrell and Pfeffer, 2014; Wilson et al., 2006).

While some aspects of data collection in the UK are supported, inconsistencies remain worldwide (ONS, 2020a). Many governments lack the capacity to collect and analyse trafficking data, even if they want to. A key reason for this is insufficient funding and poor governance, which affect the capacity to monitor and respond to human trafficking cases (Putt, 2007). As a result, available data often rely on NGOs records of assisted victims rather than comprehensive, state-led monitoring systems (ibid.).

2.4 Who are the Victims of Human Trafficking?

Victims of HT can be men, women and children of any age or nationality, although women and young girls are usually the most affected by HT (Burke et al., 2022). The most predominant form of HT remains sexual exploitation of women and girls compared to males and boys. Traffickers often target women and girls from disadvantaged countries and communities to exploit them for cheap labour and sex tourism profit (Aronowitz, 2001). According to the NCA in 2018, females represented 1,192 victims and 532 girls, while males, with 92 victims and 105 boys, were trafficked for this purpose (NCA, 2019a; ONS, 2020b).

Nevertheless, critics argue that all the attention has been placed on the trafficking of women and children for sexual exploitation, neglecting the fact that men can also be victims of exploitation for sex and/or labour slavery (Gulati, 2012). For instance, police might disregard men and boys as victims of sex trafficking because of the prevalent belief that only women and girls are exploited by sex traffickers (Gulati, 2012; Home Office, 2024). Male victims of sexual exploitation may also face additional barriers to disclosure, such as societal stigma and gendered perceptions of victimhood (Parliament. House of

Lords, 2024). Apart from this, there is currently a limited research base assessing the extent of male sexual exploitation (ibid.).

While sexual exploitation is more commonly reported, labour trafficking seems to be a problem that is growing exponentially in the UK. In 2018, 1,805 boys and 1,730 men were trafficked for labour exploitation, compared to 182 girls and 272 women (ONS, 2020b). These figures show that labour trafficking may outnumber sex trafficking, yet it remains highly under-researched and does not receive enough attention (Sweileh, 2018).

2.5 Causes of Trafficking

Mutso (2009, p. 282) declare that, although growing interdisciplinary interest, most trafficking studies continue to rely on 'push and pull factors' to explain the emergence, scale, and scope of the phenomenon. These factors often intersect in complex ways. Traffickers exploit such conditions by deliberately targeting people's weaknesses by using physical force, psychological coercion, debt manipulation, and familial bond exploitation (UNODC, 2013). Push factors include poverty, unemployment, forced migration, conflict, lack of education, war, cultural norms and discrimination against girls (Segrave, 2016; HMICFRS, 2017; Dhakal Adhikari, 2018; Such et al., 2023). Pull factors, in contrast, include economic growth/demand for cheap labour and sex work, and arranged marriages (Laczko and Gozdzik, 2005). Traffickers exploit these aspirations by offering false job opportunities in sectors like nail salons, car washes, and construction work (NCA, n.d.; Landman et al., 2024). While many victims do come from poorer regions (Newman, 2006), ATMG (2018) argues that many poor communities do not become victims of trafficking, and many of those affected by trafficking do not come from a background of abject poverty. Cho (2015) further argues that it is not ignorance or lack of education that makes women vulnerable to trafficking, but rather a lack of economic opportunity in their home countries.

2.6 Harm Caused by Human Trafficking

Human trafficking has an extremely detrimental, traumatising effect on its victims. It causes not only physical harm but also severe psychological and emotional damage. Most of the victims are diagnosed with extreme trauma, leading to long-lasting consequences. These include anxiety disorder, post-traumatic stress disorder (PTSD), depression, abuse of drugs, self-inflicted wounds, schizophrenia and psychotic disorders (Altun et al., 2017; Oram et al., 2015).

Oram et al.'s (2015) research shows that women experience higher levels of mental health symptoms than men. Their research showed that 78% of female trafficking victims suffered from depression, compared to 40% of male survivors who showed signs of depression, anxiety, and PTSD symptoms. Furthermore, female sex trafficking victims are also at higher risk of developing injuries in the urogenital and musculoskeletal regions, increasing the risk of illness and of sexually transmitted infections (STIs) and HIV (Klabbers et al., 2023; Home Affairs Committees, 2023b). Similarly, children who have been trafficked or sexually exploited are at high risk of severe mental health issues, including self-harm, suicide attempts, and long-term psychological disorders (Laser-Maira et al., 2019). The psychological impact on trafficked children is compounded by polyvictimisation, including witnessing violence and experiencing abandonment, neglect, and displacement (U.S. Department of State, 2025).

This chapter examined the multifaceted nature of human trafficking, including international definitions, critiques of the Palermo Protocol, and the UK's legal response through the Modern Slavery Act. It highlighted challenges in data accuracy, gendered vulnerabilities, socio-economic drivers, and the varied impacts on victims. The next chapter evaluates UK legal frameworks and victim support mechanisms.

Chapter 3: Legal Frameworks and Practice in the UK

3.1 Introduction

This chapter reviews the UK government's legal framework and policy response to HT and modern slavery through the analysis of the Modern Slavery Act 2015 and the NRM. It provides an overview of major legal changes and describes statutory bodies involved and victim identification practices in the current times. Finally, it will discuss the criticisms of MSA and NRM.

3.2 Legislation and Policy in the UK

The Modern Slavery Act 2015 redefines the legal terms of trafficking and slavery offences in England and Wales (Human Trafficking Foundation, 2018). Prior to this Act, there were pre-existing legislations such as the Sexual Offences Act 2003, which introduced offences for trafficking for sexual exploitation (Lipscombe and Beard, 2014), while the Immigration and Asylum Act 2004 criminalised all forms of trafficking (Broad and Turnbull, 2019).

3.3 UK Modern Slavery Act 2015

The UK Modern Slavery Act 2015 is the first national legislation to use the term 'modern slavery' (Broad and Turnbull, 2019, p.120). As has been discussed earlier, this terminology includes any form of human trafficking, labour, sexual and criminal exploitation, and domestic servitude (Home Office, 2020).

While the terms 'human trafficking' and 'modern slavery' are often used interchangeably, they actually refer to distinct concepts. For human trafficking components, see chapter 2. For modern slavery, the components are two: *means* holding a person through physical force or threats of penalty, and *service* using a person for begging, sexual services, forced labour and domestic service (Human Trafficking Foundation, 2018).

Key provisions of the MSA include the establishment of the NRM (45 days), which will be discussed later, and the duty to notify, and established the UK Independent Anti-Slavery Commissioner (IASC) (Home Office, 2025b). Set out several modern slavery offences; introduced a requirement for commercial organisations with an annual turnover over £36 million to publish yearly statements outlining steps taken to prevent modern slavery in their operations and supply chains; created

Independent Child Trafficking Guardians and provided primary legislation that sets up a statutory defence for victims of modern slavery into primary legislation (Landman et al., 2024).

3.4 Response to Modern Slavery

The UK government in 2014 adopted the Modern Slavery Strategy, also known as ‘**four P**’ framework to address modern HT (HM Government, 2014): *Pursue* - to prosecute and disrupt offenders; *Prevent* - prevent individuals from engaging in modern slavery; *Protect* - to safeguard vulnerable individuals and raise public awareness; *Prepare* - to reduce harm caused by modern slavery through improved victim identification and support (Human Trafficking Foundation, 2018).

Aligned with this strategy, the MSA 2015 provides two mechanisms to improve victim support. Section 49 requires the Secretary of State to issue guidance on identifying and supporting victims, while **Section 50** grants the authority to introduce regulations concerning victim assistance. Although the government re-committed to these in **October 2017**, neither has been implemented, leaving support inconsistent and legally unprotected (Human Trafficking Foundation, 2018). Another key provision of the Act is Section 45, which introduces a statutory defence for all victims who commit offences under any pressure (threat, deception, etc.) (HMICFRS, 2017). However, critics argue that the defence is inconsistently applied, with some genuine victims still being prosecuted, while law enforcement has raised concerns that it may be exploited by offenders falsely claiming victim status to avoid prosecution (Haughey, 2016).

3.5 Statistics in the UK

While the number of presumed and identified victims referred to the NRM in the UK has increased since 2014 (**Home Office, 2020**), the true number of actual victims is likely higher (Home Affairs Committee, 2023c). In total, 19,125 potential victims of modern slavery were referred to the NRM in 2024, a 13% increase from 2023 (16,990). Of these referred, 13,100 were adults (at age of referral), 9,459 were men, and 3,626 were women. Whilst 5,999 were children, with 4,677 being boys and 1,306 being girls. The age at referral was unknown in 26 cases. The ATMG (2012) argues that the UK is both a source and transit country for victims of trafficking. The majority of potential victims came from the UK, Albania, and Vietnam. Forty-three per cent of potential victims reported being exploited solely within the UK (Home Office, 2025a).

Figure 3: Number of NRM referrals by age group of referral

Source: SCA, IECA

Source: Home Office (2025a)

Modern slavery can affect anyone in society, with victims being exploited in several ways. For example, as Figure 7 shows:

Figure 7: Number of NRM referrals, by exploitation type and age at referral

Source: SCA, IECA

Source: Home Office (2025a)

From Figure 7, labour exploitation was the most common form of slavery reported among adults (32%) in the UK, followed by criminal exploitation (48%) of children. Males most often reported labour exploitation (39%; 5,462), while females most frequently reported sexual exploitation (31%; 1,546) (Home Office, 2025a).

3.6 Child Criminal Exploitation

Although there is no specific definition of child criminal exploitation, the term is widely used to describe various forms of coercive involvement of children in criminal activity (Barlow, 2019; The Children's Society, 2019). This includes offences such as pickpocketing, drug trafficking or cultivation, counterfeit goods, begging, fraud and sham marriage (Home Office, 2025a, b). The most common form is county lines, whereby victims, mostly UK-based children, are exploited to sell drugs in large cities, expanding their reach to small towns. They are frequently recruited to transport substances, and mobile phone 'lines' are used to communicate drug orders (Parliament. House of Lords, 2024; Home Office, 2025a, b). There are approximately 1,000 branded deal lines, with over 2,000 lines estimated to be operating, involving thousands of young people (NCA, 2019b).

In recognition of the coercive and exploitative nature of these practices, the NRM has expanded its scope in recent years to include more UK nationals alongside minors, with CL cases increasingly classified under modern slavery legislation (The Children's Society, 2019; Harding, 2020; Koch et al., 2024). In 2024, **1,845** county lines referrals were recorded, representing for 10% of all referrals received. Most 76% (1,396) of these referrals were for male children at the time of referral (Home Office, 2025a). Despite this rise, the exact number of children affected by CL remains unknown due to the lack of data collection (Maxwell et al., 2019). This is because some local authorities avoid making referrals, fearing it may harm a child's immigration status, while others lack training on trafficking indicators and their duties as First Responders ATMG (2014b). Since these figures represent only one country and are likely underestimations, the global scale of child trafficking is even more alarming (Lugris et al., 2022).

3.7 National Referral Mechanism

The National Referral Mechanism, established in 2009, is the UK's official framework for identifying and supporting victims of HT and modern slavery (Home Office, 2020). Referrals can be made by first responders, including police, public authorities, and specified NGOs. In 2024, police forces and Regional Organised Crime Units (ROCU) recorded 20% (3,822) modern slavery offences in England and Wales (Home Office, 2025a). For adults, consent is required for a referral to proceed; when they do not, the

first responder has a 'duty to notify' the Home Office (Seideman, 2015; Lumley-Sapanski et al., 2024, p.4; Home Office, 2025a, b). Whilst children under 18 do not require consent (Home Office, 2025a, b), as any child transported for exploitative purposes is automatically classified as trafficked, regardless of deception or consent (Dottridge and Jordan, 2012). Once a case is referred to the NRM, a Single Case Authority (SCA) at the Home Office will consider the case and make a reasonable grounds decision (O'Brien et al., 2022). The referral process involves two threshold decisions: the Reasonable Grounds decision, which should be made after a minimum of 5 days, and the Conclusive Grounds decision, which is expected within 45 days (Home Office, 2019; O'Brien et al., 2022; Lumley-Sapanski et al., 2024). In a positive reasonable grounds decision, the victim is entitled to mental health care, legal support, accommodation and other forms of support (Broad and Turnbull, 2019; Home Office, 2019; O'Brien et al., 2022).

However, not all individuals referred to the NRM will ultimately be assessed to be victims of modern slavery. In 2024, 20,090 reasonable grounds decisions were issued, with 53% being positive, alongside 9,501 negative reasonable grounds decisions. Of the 19,125 referrals, 17,304 received conclusive grounds decisions, with 56% positive and 7,566 negative conclusive grounds decisions (Home Office, 2025a). The increase in referrals may reflect growing awareness of modern slavery and the NRM, alongside a possible rise in exploitation. However, it is difficult to identify a single driving factor due to the complexity of the crime (ibid.).

3.8 Criticisms

3.8.1 Criticism of MSA

The Modern Slavery Act 2015 has been criticised for being a politically driven and symbolic response to exploitation, rather than a rational, evidence-based solution (Broad and Turnbull, 2019). The term "modern slavery" itself is emotive and lacks conceptual clarity, contributing to what critics call "exploitation creep," where all forms of trafficking are rebranded as slavery (Chuang, 2014, p. 611). Policymakers, particularly elite actors, shaped the law through moral discourse that overemphasised sexual exploitation while marginalising labour trafficking (Broad and Turnbull, 2019). Furthermore, the Act prioritises enforcement over victim protection, with migrant victims often treated as offenders, evident in operations such as Operation Magnify, which targeted UK nail bars, resulting in the arrest of approximately 100 migrant workers (Mason and agencies, 2016). Additionally, the Act fails to address structural causes of exploitation, while excluding human rights voices and reinforcing racialised and neoliberal narratives of victimhood (Kempadoo, 2015; Agustin, 2007). Ultimately, the legislation offers

only a partial solution, shaped by top-down decision-making that limits its real impact (Broad and Turnbull, 2019).

3.8.2 Criticism of NRM

While the NRM has successfully supported and identified victims of modern slavery in England and Wales, it has been widely criticised for its limitations. Critics argue that it is overly bureaucratic, racist (particularly with those from countries outside of EEA, and Black or from other minority ethnic backgrounds), lacks transparency and accountability (ATMG, 2014a; UN Human Rights Committee, 2020), and does not support victims well (Home Office, 2019). There is a limited understanding of how positive identification decisions are made, partly due to poor data record-keeping and restricted access to data (Schwarz and Williams-Woods, 2022). Moreover, little is known about what happens to victims after going through the NRM, raising concerns that many are left vulnerable to re-trafficking (Human Trafficking Foundation, 2016).

Victims continue to face years-long wait times for conclusive grounds decisions, which, when issued, do not grant any rights or residency permits. The support they receive ends too soon and abruptly (ATMG, 2014b; Burland, 2017). For example, the Independent Anti-Slavery Commissioner's Annual Report (2022) showed that the average waiting time for a conclusive grounds decision was 568 days. During this period, victims often face a negative impact on physical and mental health, and re-traumatisation (Murphy, 2021). Even when people receive positive conclusive grounds decisions, it does not guarantee leave to remain in the UK, leaving many undocumented victims vulnerable to detention and deportation (Human Trafficking Foundation, 2017; Esslemont, 2019; Findlay, 2024). Further problems have been identified in the NRM system. Over 200 closed cases found that potential victims were 24 % more likely to receive a referral to NRM if it was known that their recruitment occurred outside the UK, and 19% more likely when some or all exploitation happened outside the UK (O'Brien et al., 2022; Hestia, 2019). These issues are compounded by the fact that decisions are often made by individuals who lack the legal expertise to identify and support potential victims of trafficking and modern slavery correctly, further undermining the effectiveness and credibility of the NRM (UN Human Rights Committee, 2020).

Another key criticism, as seen in the MSA as well, is the confusion between the NRM and immigration control. There is a tendency for authorities to view trafficked individuals not as victims but as immigration offenders, especially in cases involving irregular migration (Craig, 2017). Likewise, victims identified through the criminal justice system are more likely to face criminal charges (e.g., prosecuted

as offenders) than supported (Andreatta, 2015; Hales and Gelsthorpe, 2012). Even in cases where they have positive conclusive grounds status or active cases (Burland, 2019). For example, women forced to commit crimes as drug mules or commit street crimes have been convicted instead of being recognised as victims (Andreatta, 2015; Hales and Gelsthorpe, 2012). Supporting this, Prison Reform Trust and Hibiscus Initiatives (2018) identified 45 imprisoned women between 2013 and 2017 as victims of MS, all of whom had disclosed experiences of exploitation. Yet they were still prosecuted and imprisoned for offences they were forced to commit.

Additionally, the NRM process frequently lacks informed consent. Many individuals are referred without understanding the system or their rights due to language barriers and trauma, and practitioners sometimes provide misleading or coercive information (O'Brien et al., 2022; Findlay, 2024). Besides this, the NRM lacks specialist support for children as well as other categories of survivors. A recent report from the Human Trafficking Foundation found that only 13% of survivors access safe houses through the MSVCC service (Modern Slavery Act 2015 Committee, 2024). This means that most survivors access alternative accommodations and outreach support. Ultimately, the NRM appears designed less to protect survivors and more to preserve the state's control, often by framing those seeking help as abusers of the system and reasserting state victimhood over that of the individuals it purports to support (Findlay, 2024).

The UK has advanced its legal system using the MSA and NRM, yet implementation difficulties and inadequate victim protection persist. The system faces criticism because it operates with poor transparency in decision-making, immigration control integration, and bureaucratic inefficiencies. The data reveals persistent problems with victimised individuals receiving inconsistent results, along with evidence showing both continued re-trafficking and racial prejudices, and a shortage of extended support services.

Chapter 4: Police Response to Victims of Human Trafficking in the UK

4.1 Introduction

This chapter will critically assess the police response to victims in the UK. It focuses on the challenges faced by police in identifying and supporting victims of HT, examining gaps in police training, awareness, multi-agency collaboration and data sharing. It also explores the consequences of inadequate victim support and trauma-informed policing.

4.2 Barriers to Victim Self-Identification

Human trafficking continues to be a worldwide phenomenon and an urgent issue, with the police in the UK playing a key role in its identification and response. Practically, human trafficking cases are inherently difficult to identify and investigate due to several barriers. Most victims do not self-identify, either because they do not acknowledge that they are being exploited or deny their victimisation due to embarrassment about actions they were coerced into (Farrell and Pfeffer, 2014). Others may remain silent due to trauma, particularly PTSD, or as a result of manipulation and control tactics used by traffickers (Home Office, 2024). Even when victims realise they are being exploited, they do not know how or where to escape due to fears of retribution from traffickers or fear of arrest and deportation by police either in the UK or elsewhere in the world (Farrell et al., 2008; Clawson et al., 2009; Davis, 2019). Such fears are often seen, particularly from immigrant communities who may be reluctant to engage with police due to previous negative experiences; or the belief that they will not be believed or helped; or originate from countries where law enforcement and public institutions have histories of corruption (Farrell et al., 2008; Brewster, 2019). Similarly, domestic sex trafficking victims have often been arrested and charged with crimes such as prostitution before the trafficking situation was acknowledged. As a result, they have little reason to believe that their interaction with the police when reporting HT victimisation would be different (Farrell and Pfeffer, 2014).

The inability to overcome language and cultural barriers stands as a major obstacle that prevents victims who are immigrants, and perhaps some domestic victims, from contacting the police, accessing services, or expressing their experiences correctly, according to Farrell and Pfeffer (2014). Police or gatekeepers may interpret the victim's believability based on cultural behaviours and differences that suggest credibility (e.g., lack of eye contact) (Clawson et al., 2004; 2009; O'Brien et al., 2022). Although

most service providers facilitate interpreters to assist with communication, the presence of a third party can affect the trust-building between the victim and supporter (Clawson et al., 2009). These communication challenges are compounded by the police's limited access to interpreters and a general lack of foreign-language skills, which impedes the identification of trafficking crimes involving foreign victims (Farrell et al., 2010).

4.3 Challenges in Police Victim Identification

Human trafficking victimisation commonly takes place out of sight of the police or other watchful guardians with incentives to report a crime (Farrell and Pfeffer, 2014). Although efforts have been made to improve police training and awareness, many victims still go unnoticed, as police often fail to recognise clear signs of exploitation (National Audit Office, 2017). This is partly due to a general lack of knowledge about HT, limited police awareness, and differing definitions and perceptions regarding who is considered a victim (Clawson et al., 2004). Moreover, Vijayarasa (2016), Farrell et al. (2014), and Mapp et al. (2016) argue that police responses are often shaped by stereotypes, expecting victims to display signs of physical injuries; visible trauma; or assuming that only foreign nationals are victims. Thereby, officers may overlook victims whose exploitation is less overt or visible. Additionally, some police may wrongly assume that trafficking always involves transportation or movement and that sex trafficking is the only form of exploitation (Farrell et al., 2014; Mapp et al., 2016). Yet, such misconceptions may also account for the under-identification of certain forms of exploitation, including labour exploitation and domestic servitude (Barrick et al., 2014; Farrell and Pfeffer, 2014). Even when trafficking offences are correctly identified, police may struggle to act effectively due to gaps in their knowledge of anti-trafficking legislation and policy (Newton et al., 2008).

4.4 Misclassification of Victims by Police

Even when victims reach the police's attention, they may be misclassified. Police on the street often resolve problems based on routines, which help them navigate ambiguous legal definitions, which can lead to crimes like HT being easily misclassified (Bittner, 1967; Skolnick, 1966). Unlike new crimes that require police to learn specific elements and indicators (Carter and Katz, 1996), HT demands a shift in how long-standing offences are perceived. For instance, police are familiar with and may have set routines for investigating prostitution. Consequently, they might automatically view a woman engaged in prostitution as a perpetrator rather than a potential crime victim (Farrell et al., 2010; Farrell and Pfeffer, 2014).

Another reason for the misclassification of victims is that police conceptualisations of HT often overlap with the definition of migrant smuggling, frequently treating both acts as one and the same. As a result, victims may be mistakenly classified as smuggled persons who have committed migration offences (Farrell et al., 2010; see Ch. 3). Although these terms have been clearly defined and differentiated in international law and UN protocols, experts still debate their distinctions (Irwin, 2017). This ambiguity can cause confusion in practice, leading to blurred interpretations at the enforcement level (Bilger et al., 2006). Smuggling is sometimes perceived as a humanitarian act, yet the lack of clarity in distinguishing between smuggling and trafficking increases the risk of victims being wrongly identified as offenders rather than as individuals needing protection (Achilli, 2018).

4.5 Criminalisation of Victims by Police

In addition to the broader issue of misclassification, many UK police have been criticised for treating victims as offenders, particularly in cases involving sex workers. Victims are often arrested, deported or prosecuted for offences committed under duress by traffickers rather than identifying or prosecuting actual traffickers (Davies, 2009; Doezema, 2010; Anderson and Li, 2018). In some cases, police may not record a prostitution offence at all, believing that it is more beneficial for the adolescent to either be released or charged with another offence, such as disorderly conduct or trespassing. Police decisions may also be affected by other factors, such as the adolescent's behaviour, the officer's sympathy for a teenager and specific law enforcement policies within the jurisdiction (Finkelhor and Ormrod, 2004).

Another misclassification is seen in the case of a young Albanian man, who in February 2023 was sentenced to 13 months in prison for cannabis cultivation after being smuggled into the UK on a small boat. He was promised work in construction, but upon arrival, his documents were taken, and he was threatened with his life and family. Traffickers told him he owed £10,000 for his journey and forced him to work to repay the debt, or he would be killed. He was confined to a property where cannabis plants were already growing. This demonstrates that despite clear signs of trafficking and forced criminality, the police and courts failed to understand and identify him as a victim rather than as an offender (Modern Slavery Act 2015 Committee, 2024).

This criminalisation trend also appears in child exploitation cases, particularly involving county lines. For example, children exploited through CL are often arrested for minor offences before being identified as HT victims (Davis, 2019; Hestia, 2019). Such cases highlight a broader issue in police responses, where exploited children are frequently mistreated as criminals rather than victims (Sturrock and Holmes, 2015; Espeute and Lanskey, 2023). This happens partly due to a punitive youth justice

approach that overlooks structural factors like grooming (Sturrock and Holmes, 2015) or assumes they have made a lifestyle choice, which can result in victims feeling blamed and unsupported (Fogg, 2008). Christie's (1986) and O'Brien's (2013) 'ideal victim' concept explains why such children may not be recognised as victims because they do not always fit the stereotype of a weak; blameless victim; may know their exploiters; and are involved in drug sales. Davis (2019) argues that trafficked victims should not be prosecuted under any circumstances because many victims may have escaped exploitation and are living independently without any help or assistance.

4.6 Lack of Awareness and Training among Police

Effective anti-trafficking policing faces its biggest hurdle from insufficient training and a lack of awareness among officers. Victims of trafficking may sometimes be discovered through routine police activities, such as responding to domestic violence incidents or immigration offences. Yet, police may fail to identify them due to limited awareness (Richards and Lyneham, 2014; HMICFRS, 2017). One such case involved a 48-year-old Chinese woman discovered during a police raid on a suspected brothel in 2017 in the UK. She was arrested for immigration violations, but further investigations showed she was legally in the UK. When police returned her to the address, she expressed fear of the man running the business, yet she was left outside. Later, police suspected she might be a trafficking victim. The authorities could not find her after discharge, which probably meant she was at risk of continued exploitation and re-trafficking (HMICFRS, 2017). This case reflects poor communication between police about victims, which increases the likelihood of offenders exploiting them again in other areas. Law enforcers concentrate on stopping criminal activity instead of protecting victims, which reduces their ability to stop HT operations (Pajon and Walsh, 2022).

Police training on HT remains inadequate and under-researched. Jannetta, McCoy and Leitson (2018) note that while training was not included in the original Palermo Protocol 2000, it has since emerged as a critical issue. However, only a few studies have investigated the effect of training (Renzetti et al, 2015). Most reports on HT training exist only to mention that it occurs, such as the UK's Home Office (2011) report, which mentions its importance but lacks any analysis of how or why it should be provided. While some research on police training effectiveness exists (Marion, 1998), the focus on HT-specific training is limited, and existing studies are outdated (Renzetti et al., 2015).

These challenges are also visible in police practice. Hestia's (2019) report showed that only a small percentage of police forces include HT training in their continuous development programs. While specialist modern slavery units within certain police forces, like the Metropolitan Police or Greater

Manchester Police, may have greater expertise, this knowledge does not always reach frontline officers (Hestia, 2019). Many police receive only basic training early in their careers but may not encounter trafficking cases for years, meaning their knowledge becomes outdated (Van Dyke and Brachou, 2021; Hestia, 2019). This is evident in that many police officers do not receive adequate training on specific trafficking indicators, such as forced labour in nail bars, domestic servitude, or coerced shoplifting (Drugan, 2019).

Despite these limitations, there have been signs of progress in the UK's response to HT. For instance, police operations Pentameter 1 successfully identified 85 victims of trafficking for sexual exploitation, including 12 children from 20 different countries (Gloucestershire Constabulary, 2006, cited in Scullion, 2015).

4.7 Need for Centralised and Trauma-Informed Training

According to Superintendent Mark Edgington, even in large forces, the number of specialists remains inadequate, limiting their ability to pass on knowledge to frontline officers (Edgington, 2021). In their evidence to the Home Affairs Select Committee, West Yorkshire Police said that in a police force of over 7,000, a team of 15 specialists is a small number and called for more specialist staff to pass on their knowledge and advice to officers in the front line (Home Affairs Committee, 2024). This highlights the need for centralised training programs to ensure all officers possess basic competencies in recognising and responding to HT. Centralised training would also reduce regional disparities, ensuring consistent standards nationwide (HMICFRS, 2021).

Police encounter difficulties when detecting trauma-based behaviours, particularly fear dissociation and uncooperative behaviour, since these symptoms commonly resemble criminal conduct (Gadd and Broad, 2018; Lee, 2013). The social challenges become more severe because institutions do not employ trauma-informed practices. When victims demonstrate distress patterns unlike those considered 'ideal', they face dismissal, so authorities lose trust while failing to protect them effectively (Home Office, 2024). Additionally, as mentioned earlier, the perception that women are more vulnerable to HT may result in male victims being overlooked (Barron and Frost, 2018). This could be compounded by a lack of police training in supporting male victims. Research showed that police were seeking advice on how to support male victims from HT activists and volunteers (Ricard-Guay and Hanley, 2020). In other words, police forces around the globe may receive very little training on how to support male victims of trafficking themselves. Consequently, there remains a significant gap in research regarding police understanding of male victims of trafficking.

4.8 Limitations in Multi-Agency Collaboration

4.8.1 Barriers to International and Domestic Police Collaboration

A key challenge for law enforcement is that human trafficking is a borderless crime, evolving across international, national, and local borders, making it both a local and global issue that requires a collaborative and multi-agency response (McGeer, 2017, cited in Saker, 2022). In the UK, such collaboration plays a crucial role in shaping the police response to trafficking victims, particularly as the country is recognised as one of the foremost destination countries for trafficking (U.S. Department of State, 2024). However, despite its recognised importance, police forces often struggle to determine which agencies to collaborate with and for what purpose, leading to inconsistencies in investigative practices (Crawford and L’Hoiry, 2017; HMICFRS, 2017; IASC and University of Nottingham, 2017). In 2019 (HMICFRS, 2022), public service personnel who separately knew of a Vietnamese trafficking victim did not adequately exchange information and, as a result, delayed protection and victim re-exploitation.

International police collaboration is often hindered by poor coordination and communication between police forces (Wheaton et al., 2010). These obstacles stem from variations in criminal justice systems, laws, police practices and procedures, states’ abilities to tackle crime, and the lack of effective mechanisms for international cooperation (Reichel, 2008; Dandurand, 2017).

In England and Wales, despite the recognition of the importance of multi-agency collaboration in key guidance documents, such as the Government’s Modern Slavery strategy (HM Government, 2014) and the UK’s College of Policing (2019), the practical implementation remains inconsistent. The official police watchdog also found that the application of such practices by police forces was uneven across England and Wales (HMICFRS, 2017). Additionally, while guidelines for multi-agency cooperation exist, there is no standardised strategy or protocol for cooperation, leading many police officers to rely on informal connections and previous professional experiences to guide their collaborative efforts (Wilson and Dalton, 2008). Such a lack of shared understanding may explain the limitations and uneven application of police collaboration across forces when investigating trafficking cases (Haughey, 2016; HMICFRS, 2017). For instance, the HMICFRS (2017) report found that there was poor coordination and communication among police forces when a trafficking victim was identified in a different police area from where the exploitation took place. This resulted in delays in investigations and insufficient victim support. Moreover, while some international collaboration was evident in the report, international intelligence checks were often not utilised, especially in the early stages of investigations. The report also noted that many investigators lacked knowledge on conducting international intelligence checks

through the NCA (HMICFRS, 2017). Finally, multi-agency collaboration is important not only for intelligence purposes but also for identifying better and safeguarding victims of HT (Farrell et al., 2008; Gerassi et al., 2017; Matos et al., 2018; Wilson and Dalton, 2008).

4.8.2 Challenges in Information Sharing and Data Collection

Beyond coordination issues, information sharing remains a significant barrier to effective anti-trafficking efforts, even within and between police forces (HMICFRS, 2017). One significant issue is siloed data, where crucial information is restricted to the agency that collects it, hindering intelligence-led investigations (U.S. Department of State, 2019). Furthermore, while many of the agencies that currently assist victims of trafficking around the world collect a great deal of information about trafficking, only a few of these agencies analyse and share the information they collect systematically (Laczko and Gramegna, 2003). Limiting the ability to learn, understand, and improve anti-trafficking strategies (ONS, 2020a).

Not all trafficking cases are reported. And even when they are, different agencies such as the US Government, the ILO, the UNODC, the International Organisation for Migration (IOM), Ministry of Justice (MoJ), and Office for National Statistics (ONS) use different data collection methods, as each has a distinct perspective and understanding of data collection (Scullion, 2015; ONS, 2020a). Each organisation listed above collects data per their mandates, which means that people may be counted in multiple datasets, which may lead to misidentification of trafficking victims (Scullion, 2015). For instance, in the London Metropolitan Police in 2003, out of 295 women, only four or five were identified as victims of trafficking, whilst the rest were found to be in breach of UK immigration law. This does not necessarily indicate that there is very little trafficking (O'Connell Davidson, 2006).

4.8.3 Victim Support and Victim-Centred Policing and Its Long-Term Impact

The concepts of victim-centred policing and victim support share an overlapping connection but operate as separate entities. Victim-centred policing describes law enforcement strategies which maintain survivors' dignity alongside their agency and trauma background information during the investigative process. Victim support encompasses full-range assistance, including legal, psychological and practical programs that direct victims to healthcare housing and recovery services (Home Office, 2020). A thorough examination of how inadequate victim identification damages protective measures was presented in the earlier sections. This section explores the direct effects of investigation failures by identifying systemic barriers which block meaningful support for victims.

Trauma-informed policing implementation shows inconsistent progress, even though various policies claim support for this approach. The responses survivors face from police often include communication challenges combined with urgent interrogation techniques and prejudice against their cultural background (Drugan, 2019). This mirrors the difficulties outlined by Helfferich et al. (2011), who found that building trust and showing empathy were key to victims' willingness to engage with police.

Trauma-informed practices can help mitigate the challenges faced by survivors, as improper victim interviews can re-traumatise them, creating more barriers to providing accurate testimony (Meshkovska et al., 2016). As outlined in chapter 2, HT has a significant impact on psychological as well as physical health and wellbeing. Police officers often misunderstand trauma symptoms, such as dissociative states or silence, interpreting them as suspicious actions instead of signs of victimisation (Vijayarasa, 2016; Gadd and Broad, 2018). Survivors commonly report that rather than being supported, police subject them to disbelief, accusatory questioning, and a lack of procedural assistance (Ooher and Olsson, 2017). According to ECPAT UK (2024), these barriers prevent survivors from participating due to delayed legal procedures, insufficient interpreter assistance, and communication failures. The failure to recognise trauma and the tendency to treat victims based on preconceived stereotypes or biases can impede the development of a victim-centred approach. This leads to further mistrust and disengagement with the justice system (HMICFRS, 2023). Just as Helfferich et al. (2011) discussed the barriers to obtaining reliable testimonies, these prejudices and interrogation tactics undermine efforts to provide effective victim support. Victims may be reluctant to share their experiences due to fear of mistreatment or cultural misunderstandings (*ibid*). Furthermore, the shortage of qualified interpreters worsens the situation. Officers frequently rely on untrained personnel or technological resources, leading to information inaccuracies and breaches of confidentiality (Drugan, 2019). This further erodes the relationship between law enforcement and victims, making it harder to obtain accurate information and exacerbating the victim's distress.

Early failures by police during investigations of victims not only produce long-lasting effects on the justice process but also hinder victim recovery. When survivors face criminalisation along with denial or disbelief, they become less likely to assist investigations, and this hampers the success of trafficking network investigations (Palumbo, 2024). For instance, in 2022, the number of trafficking prosecutions in England and Wales was only 405, according to data from the Crown Prosecution Service (Home Affairs Committee, 2023a), despite the clear need for more. Victims coerced into committing illegal activities, such as drug offences, can be left with criminal records that prevent them from accessing

critical services such as housing, education, or immigration relief. This exacerbates their risk of social exclusion and re-exploitation (Espeute and Lanskey, 2023; RUSI, 2023).

This chapter found that the HT response by UK police forces continues to face longstanding operational failings during victim support operations and communication with other agencies. Real change necessitates operational reform combined with trauma-informed practice and survivor-centred approaches to recognise victims properly and provide their necessary protection and empowerment.

Chapter 5: Conclusion

This dissertation critically examined the United Kingdom's criminal justice legal responses to victims of human trafficking. Significant operational and systemic challenges persist despite strong legislative frameworks such as the MSA 2015 and the NRM. This reveals a serious gap between policy and practice, where laws exist on paper but fail to deliver meaningful protection in reality, leaving victims vulnerable and traffickers undeterred.

Critically reflecting on the analysis above, it becomes clear that the challenges are not merely operational, but deeply structural. The push and pull factors, such as poverty, war, demand for cheap labour, and sexual exploitation, have driven individuals into trafficking, offering a valuable lens to understand its complexity (Mutso, 2009; Segrave, 2016; HMICFRS, 2017; Dhakal Adhikari, 2018; Such et al., 2023). Although these global drivers may not be easily resolved, an informed understanding of them is essential in shaping more effective and empathetic responses. This involves not only training and structural reform, but a shift in cultural and institutional thinking. Recognising that trafficking victims may not always present themselves in expected ways, and intersectional factors like race, gender, immigration status, and socio-economic background shape that vulnerability.

The UK's anti-trafficking response is shaped by tensions between victim protection and immigration enforcement, often treating victims as irregular migrants rather than individuals entitled to support and justice (Craig, 2017). Police responses cannot be detached from these broader forces. When victims are disbelieved, misidentified, or retraumatised through procedural failures, the state inadvertently reinforces the same inequalities that make trafficking possible. Such an approach weakens trust, discourages disclosure, and undermines both victim welfare and law enforcement effectiveness.

Overall, despite the growing international recognition of the complex realities of trafficking, policing and victim support in the UK remain overly reliant on narrow, simplistic models of exploitation. Survivors who do not conform to the "ideal victim" stereotype are less likely to be identified and supported, exposing deep biases within the system (Christie, 1986; O'Brien, 2013; Home Office, 2024). These biases not only perpetuate inequality but also undermine the effectiveness of anti-trafficking efforts. To make meaningful progress, the UK must adopt a more inclusive approach that recognises the diverse experiences of all trafficking victims.

Many recommendations could be made in view of this research, the central recommendations are as follows: (1) All police forces should be trained for HT and trauma-informed victim engagement (HMICFRS, 2017); (2) improve information sharing between police and other agencies to speed up the exchange of intelligence regarding HT and MS (HMICFRS 2017); (3) implement reforms to the NRM to facilitate the timely determination of victim status that do not discourage victims from coming forward, particularly undocumented migrants (U.S. Government, 2024); (4) ensure consistency across NRM decision-making for foreign and UK national victims and provide all victims access to the same quality of decisions and services (U.S. Government, 2024).

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